

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART III. VISCOSITY OF SHELLAC SOLUTIONS IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

BY SANTI RANJAN PALIT.

The viscosity of shellac dissolved in a solvent mixture composed of two non-solvents, acetone and water has been studied over a wide range of concentration and temperature. The viscosity-solvent composition curves show well-defined minimum at a definite ratio of water to acetone in the solvent mixture for shellac concentration of 25% and higher; the lower the temperature, the more sharp and well-defined are the minima. For lower concentrations of shellac below 20% the viscosity continually rises with increase in the proportion of water. This striking difference in properties in shellac solutions in aqueous acetone below and above 20% of shellac has also been noted in the case of some other properties, e.g., gelation capacity, temperature coefficient of relative viscosity, etc., for which either solvation or micelle formation has been suggested as explanation. The solvent power as determined by precipitation with an inert solvent like benzene, or by cooling, always shows a maximum at about 80% water content. Thus the idea that viscosity is a criterion of solvent power is shown to be of restricted validity.

Viscosity data for solutions in a mixture of solvents, where neither of the components alone can dissolve the substance but the mixture has good solvent power, are valuable from theoretical as well as technical points of view. It has been observed by the author (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 308) that resins show solubility in a mixture of two non-solvents. Thus shellac (pure resin) is soluble in a mixture composed of either acetone or methyl acetate as one component, and water or glycol as the other, though none of the above-mentioned solvents dissolves the pure dry resin. These systems are particularly suitable for viscosity studies in mixed solvents as they are generally free from many disturbing effects usually associated with substances like cellulose derivatives, proteins, etc. These solutions as shown by the author in a previous paper (Palit, *ibid.*, 1940, 17, 537) are non-colloidal, have comparatively low viscosities (at least 1000 times lower than cellulose esters of the same concentration), are amenable to experimentation at high concentrations (even up to 50% or more) and show fairly reproducible behaviour. The present paper deals with viscosity studies of such systems under varying conditions of concentrations and temperatures. An attempt has also been made to study the relationships between viscosity and solvent power. The latter being determined by the method of precipitation by the addition of a non-solvent or by lowering of temperature.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Apparatus and Method.

Dewaxed shellac, powered to 100 mesh and dried at 42° in vacuum for 4 hours, was stored in a vacuum desiccator and used as required. Each lot was finished within a few days as standing over sulphuric acid for any length of time might induce insolubility in the shellac. The solvents were of Merck's chemically pure quality, which were dried and purified by distillation by usual procedure.

Viscosity measurements were carried out in Hoesppler viscometer (industrial type) using appropriate balls (A and B), temperature being controlled by circulating water round the viscometer tube from a thermostat kept at $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

Solutions were prepared by weighing out shellac in stoppered conical flask and adding to it the necessary volumes of solvents from appropriate burettes and microburettes. To hasten solution, the flask was placed in a water-bath at about 40°, and after the whole had dissolved, which usually took about 5 minutes or less, the solution was quickly filtered through a No. 1 or No. 2 fritted glass filter to free it from the traces of extraneous insoluble impurities (less than 0.1%). The viscosity does not depend on the method of preparation or time. In fact, it was observed that even on gelation of the solution on keeping at lower temperature and remelting it, the viscosity assumed the same value at temperatures higher than the gelation temperature by 5° or more. Similarly, the time factor was also tested.

Solvent power as determined by precipitation with a non-solvent could not be measured by using the inert petroleum fraction such as heptane as advocated by Davidson and Reid (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1927, 19, 977) due to its limited miscibility with the shellac solutions in question. Dry benzene or toluene was used which was added drop by drop to a known weight of shellac solution kept in a test tube immersed in a thermostat at 25° or 30°, until the first appearance of haziness could be observed.

Precipitation temperatures were measured by immersing a small quantity (5 c.c.) of the solution contained in test tubes in water kept inside a thermoflask whose temperature was gradually lowered in steps of a quarter of a degree every five or ten minutes. The temperature at which opalescence could be observed in ten minutes was taken to be the precipitation temperature. Gelation temperature was observed by the same procedure; the point at which the liquid did not flow on inversion of the test tube was taken as the gelation temperature.

The method of expressing concentration is as follows. A 30% shellac solution in aqueous acetone containing 10% water means that the solution contains 30 g. of shellac to 70 g. of solvent, the latter being composed of 10% water and 90% acetone by weight.

Viscosity and Concentration.

Viscosity is influenced by various factors including concentration, temperature and composition of the solvent. The variation of viscosity with concentration of shellac is shown in Fig. 1 (curves AI, II, III and IV and BI, II, III, IV). It will be observed that like all lyophilic compounds, *e.g.* polystyrenes, rubber, cellulose esters, etc., the relationship is not a linear one; the viscosity rises slowly at first and then rapidly afterwards with concentration. From the graph it may be observed that the rapid rise takes place for concentrations higher than 20% of shellac.

FIG. 1.

No formula is sufficient to represent the curves over the whole range of concentration. Einstein's formula is evidently inapplicable. If according to Bingham ("Viscosity and Plasticity," p. 202), fluidity, $\phi (= 1/\eta)$ is plotted against concentration, straight lines are not obtained but like nitrocellulose solutions (Bingham, *loc. cit.*, p. 280) a definite asymptotic curvature is observed as shown by a few typical curves in Fig. 1 (D curves). Arrhenius' formula, $\log \eta/\eta_0 = C \log A$ (Hatschek, "Viscosity of Liquids," 1929, p. 114) is to some extent applicable as shown by the $\log \eta - C$ curves in Fig. 1 (CI, II, etc.). It should be pointed out that though the points are approximately linear for 20% or higher concentrations, for lower concentrations, e.g. 10% or so, the formula is totally inadequate and the points representing these concentrations are widely out of the straight lines obtained by joining the corresponding other points.

Viscosity and Composition of Solvents.

With the same percentage weight of the solute, if the ratio of water to acetone in the solvent mixture is changed, the viscosity of the solution is profoundly influenced. Some typical curves are shown for shellac concentrations of 10, 20, 25, 30 and 35% in the graphs (Fig. 2—6) and relevant

FIG. 2.
Viscosity of 10% shellac in acetone-water.

data presented in Table I. It will be observed from the graphs that all the curves containing 30 or 35% shellac show minima at a concentration of water slightly greater than 10%. For 25% shellac the curves for lower temperatures (20° and 25°) show definite minima whereas the curves at 35° and 40° only tend to show the minima as a slight sag in the curve at that composition. This minimum viscosity occurs unlike the other curves on the initial portion of the curves at a concentration of less than 10% of water

which is due to the fact that the gelation temperatures of these solutions containing small quantities of water are close to the temperature of measurement and so the initial portions have high viscosities and on increase of water concentration the gels are gradually broken down to mobile fluids.

FIG. 3.

Viscosity of 20% shellac in acetone-water.

For 20% shellac concentration, the minima are absent but perhaps a small sag is still noticeable in the curves for lower temperatures. For 10% shellac concentration, no trace of minima is noticeable but the viscosity continually rises with increase in water content of the solvent. To sum up, the minima appear in the viscosity-solvent composition curves for concentrations of 25% or more of shellac, more prominently the lower the temperature but for lower concentrations (*e.g.* 10% shellac) no minima exist, the general shape of the curves being the same as the viscosity diagram of the pure solvent mixture.

TABLE I.

Viscosity of shellac solutions in aqueous acetone.

% Water in acetone.	Ppt. or gel. temp.	Viscosity (centipoise) at				
		20°.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.
Shellac = 10%.						
5.0	12.5°	0.824	0.761	0.702	0.652	0.610
10.0	3.0	0.987	0.899	0.827	0.757	0.696
15.0	7.0	1.241	1.099	0.988	0.897	0.825
20.0	12.5	1.454	1.273	1.127	1.011	0.943
25.0	30.5	—	—	—	1.222	1.072

TABLE I (contd.).

% Water in acetone.	Ppt. or gel. temp.	Viscosity (centipoise) at				
		20°.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.
Shellac=20%.						
2.5	—	—	—	—	1.512	1.316
5.0	—	—	2.52	1.991	1.671	1.478
10.0	—	3.22	2.641	2.226	1.941	1.716
15.0	—	—	3.161	2.565	2.218	1.996
20.0	—	—	4.069	3.077	2.617	2.278
Shellac=25%.						
2.5	20.0°	gel	6.080	3.622	2.770	2.319
5.0	12.5	7.288	4.734	3.485	2.848	2.417
10.0	2.75	7.015	4.864	3.841	3.170	2.707
15.0	5.5	7.829	6.092	4.499	3.669	3.098
20.0	10.0	—	—	5.257	4.142	3.458
Shellac=30%.						
2.5	22.0	gel	gel	10.2	6.36	4.83
5.0	17.5	53.5	13.9	8.77	6.27	4.88
10.0	12.0	19.82	11.0	7.81	5.92	4.79
15.0	10.5	19.91	11.55	7.83	6.06	4.89
20.0	14.5	34.6	16.2	10.1	7.34	5.77
25.0	24.0	—	—	16.4	9.80	7.21
Shellac=35%.						
2.5	23.25	—	565.0	23.04	12.16	8.27
5.0	20.0	—	41.31	17.19	10.73	7.87
10.0	16.25	—	15.5	9.91	7.16	5.61
15.0	17.25	—	31.61	16.82	11.32	8.59
20.0	21.25	—	60.5	25.83	15.47	11.11

Viscosity and Solvent Power.

The precipitation temperature-solvent composition curves show minima at the compositions corresponding to the minima in the viscosity curves. Even where the viscosity curves show no minima but tend to rise continually, the precipitation temperature curves exhibit the minima as usual.

This is shown in the dotted curves in Figs. 2-6, where the temperature of precipitation or gelation which is a measure of solvent power in the reciprocal sense, has been plotted. Also the dilution ratio (*i.e.* the volume of benzene or toluene necessary to be added to just precipitate shellac from one gram of solution), which may be regarded as constituting a direct measure of solvent power (though such an assumption is not free from objection as can be inferred from the work of Davidson and Reid, *loc. cit.*) always tends to show maxima at the composition corresponding to the minima in the viscosity curves. The following figures for 10%, 20% and 30% shellac solutions are, however, sufficient to establish the general trend as mentioned above.

TABLE II.

Percentage of shellac in solution.	Dilution ratio					
	Percentage of water in the solvent mixture.					
	2.5%.	5%.	10%.	15%.	20%.	25%.
10%	—	0.79	0.57	1.47*	0.22	—
25%	0.69	0.81	0.53	0.39	0.19	—
30%	0.58	0.64	0.67	0.31	0.18	0.09

To sum up, therefore, the solvent power as determined by both the methods always shows maxima at a definite ratio of water to acetone in the

* Shellac could not be precipitated even by this maximum amount of benzene miscible with the solution.

solvent mixture regardless of the concentration of the solute or of the nature of the viscosity curves.

DISCUSSION.

It is generally believed as a result of the viscometric studies of Gibson and McCall (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, **39**, 172T), Masson and McCall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 819), Highfield (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, **22**, 57), McBain, Harvey and Smith (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 212), on nitrocellulose solution and of Barr and Bircumshaw (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, **16**, 99), Mardles (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, **42**, 207T) and Sheppard, Carver and Houck (*Coll. Sym. Mon.*, 1927, **5**, 243), etc., on cellulose acetate solutions that some optimum composition exists for solvent mixtures composed either of two non-solvents or of one solvent and another latent solvent. At this optimum composition the solvent power as determined by any of the various empirical methods widely used in the nitrocellulose lacquer industry is maximum and the viscosity is correspondingly a minimum, since it is a generally accepted fact that the lower the viscosity, the higher the solvent power. This is expressed by Durran ("Solvents," 1933, 3rd Ed., p.2), as 'The viscosity of a solution of cellulose nitrate in mixtures of ether and alcohol is dependent on the ratio of ether to alcohol and reaches a minimum at a definite ratio. This ratio is a characteristic property of the particular cellulose nitrate but does not depend on the amount of it in the solution.'

FIG. 5.
Viscosity of 30% shellac in acetone-water.

The present work, however, demonstrates that the existence of minima in the viscosity-solvent composition curve is not a general behaviour but occurs only when the concentration of shellac exceeds certain value (about 20% of shellac). The fact that the nature of the curve changes below and above a certain concentration is of greater significance than what only appears from the above diagrams and a comparison of the properties of the system below and above this concentration offers certain other singularities.

It has been observed that all solutions above this minimum concentration (20-25%) form transparent, clear, thermoreversible gels on cooling, whereas on cooling a shellac solution, which is below this minimum concentration, the solid separates out as flakes or curd with scarcely any tendency towards forming a transparent jelly. From a concentration of about 20%

FIG. 6.

and upwards, the solution on cooling becomes somewhat hazy due to the separation of a number of flakes and then it forms a clear gel in which the flakes may be seen embedded. The amount of flakes separating during gelation gradually decreases as the concentration increases until at just above 25% shellac concentration, gelation absolutely free from precipitation takes place. This gradual transition from precipitation through curd-formation to gelation, perhaps shows that an increase of concentration brings about some fundamental change in the nature of a closer relationship between the solvent and the solute.

Of course, this may mean simply that just like other lyophilic, e.g. gelatine, cellulose acetate, etc., for which a minimum concentration of the colloid is necessary for gelation as observed by various workers of which a summary is given by Mardles (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **19**, 1118), this minimum gelation concentration is unusually high for the shellac system and happens to be at 20-25% of shellac. Though this is mainly correct, the already mentioned peculiarities in the viscosity-solvent composition curve and viscosity-concentration curve are also worthy of notice. Besides, though Arrhenius' equation is approximately valid above this concentration, it totally ceases to be so below a concentration of 20%.

A comparative study of the temperature coefficient of relative viscosity, as has been done in Fig. 7 where η/η_0 has been plotted against temperature, η and η_0 signifying the viscosity of the solution and the solvent respectively at the same temperature, reveals some interesting features. It is clear from the almost horizontal course of the graph that upto the minimum concentration referred to, the temperature coefficient of the solution is slightly higher than that of the pure solvent, whereas for higher concentration (say 25%, 30% or higher) the relative viscosity falls steeply with temperature. The latter behaviour is characteristic of all lyophilic substances (Hatschek, *loc. cit.*, p. 114), whereas for lyophobic substances, relative viscosity maintains about a constant value over a wide range of temperature. The conclusion seems irresistible that over a small range of concentration of the solute, it changes from lyophobic to lyophilic nature, and perhaps this transition to the lyophilic state is responsible for the gel-forming property of the solution. The high temperature coefficient of viscosity particularly near about gelation point is also worthy of notice. The viscosity amounts to a few poises only at three or four degrees higher than the gelation point and within this small range of temperature the viscosity rises to infinity (i.e. the solution gels). This is shown graphically for a few typical solutions in Fig. 7.

FIG. 7.

A. Relative viscosity-temp. curves. B. Temp. coeff. of viscosity of shellac.

All the above observations may also be explained from considerations of the colloid nature of such solutions, though it has been previously shown by the author (*loc. cit.*) and also by Houwink "Nature und Kunstharzen", 1934, p. 206) from viscometric studies that at least in dilute solutions shellac and most other natural resins exist in the truly dissolved state. It may be that over the small range of concentration through which gelation properties appear, micelles are being formed by the reversible association of resin molecules, and this may be responsible for the latter behaviour of the system. The existence of micellar aggregates in concentrated solutions to which is to be primarily attributed the gelation capacity of the system, is gradually weakened by the initial addition of water, perhaps due to adsorption of water on the smaller units to form a protective layer, with consequent decrease of viscosity and increase of solvent power. The final increase of viscosity

with further addition of water may, on this view, be explained as due to increased micelle formation as a result of decrease in solubility of the resin by the addition of a non-solvent water. The parallelism of this hypothesis with the behaviour of soap solutions is only too apparent, since the existence of a critical micellar concentration for the aqueous soap solution have recently been proved (Hartley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2347), beyond dispute. The parallelism with soap further consists in that like shellac system in question, alcoholic solutions of soap are molecularly disperse at least in dilute solutions, though soapy solutions in organic solvents are well known (*vide*, Lederer, "Kolloidchemie der Seifen," pp. 78, 229), to produce very stiff jellies on cooling.

It is easy to see from the literature why previous workers invariably obtained a minimum in the viscosity-solvent composition curves. They have always directed their work to such concentrations of the solute as are well above the minimum gelation concentration, which is very low (less than 0.5%) for substances like cellulose esters, rubber, etc., which have hitherto been the main objects of investigation.

Since, as already pointed out, the solvent power-solvent composition curves always exhibit maxima even for low concentrations of shellac (10%) where the viscosity continually increases with increase in the concentration of water, the solvent power is in no way parallel or related to the viscosity of the solution. A solvent containing about 10 to 15% water may, in this case, be justly regarded a better solvent than one containing, say 5% water, because from the latter the dissolved shellac is more easily precipitated by a lowering of temperature or by the addition of a non-solvent; but the viscosity of the former solution is certainly much higher than the latter (Fig. 4). We may, therefore, qualify the prevalent general belief first expressed by Schwartz and upheld by McBain and co-workers (*loc. cit.*), that "the best solvents yield solution of lowest apparent viscosities", by adding that this is true only above the minimum gelation concentration but may sometimes totally fail below this minimum concentration.

Acknowledgments are gratefully made to Dr. H. K. Sen, Director, Indian Lac Research Institute, for his kind interest and advice, and to my colleague, Mr. G. N. Bhattacharya, for kindly carrying out a few measurements recorded in the paper.